

Adaptive continuity-preserving simplification of street networks

Martin Fleischmann^{*1}, Anastassia Vybornova^{†2,3}, James D. Gaboardi^{‡4}, Anna Brázdová^{§1}
and Daniela Dančejová^{¶1}

¹Charles University, Albertov 6, 128 00 Prague, CZ

²University of Copenhagen, Øster Farimagsgade 5A, 1353 Copenhagen, DK

³IT University of Copenhagen, Rued Langgaards Vej 7, 2300 Copenhagen, DK

⁴Oak Ridge National Laboratory, P.O. Box 2008, 37831 Oak Ridge, TN, USA

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Summary

While street network data are nearly universally available, their representation is usually transportation-based. However, for many types of analyses, e.g., urban morphology or network science, unprocessed transportation-based street network data is unsuitable, making a cumbersome manual simplification process necessary. To address this challenge, in this paper we propose an algorithm for simplification of street networks, based on the detection of network portions that need to be simplified, and continuity-preserving heuristics that generate new geometries. The algorithm, released in the open-source Python package `neatnet`, facilitates the generation of morphological networks and generalises to various geographical contexts without a need to alter the parameters, while offering better performance than other available solutions.

KEYWORDS: streets, networks, simplification, pre-processing, morphology

1 Introduction

Street networks, as objects of study, are present in research across a broad spectrum of disciplines, from transportation to urban planning and economics. With large-scale data (e.g., from OpenStreetMap or Overture Maps) and analyses appearing on the web and in literature (Boeing, 2018), advances in open-source software are making it easier than ever to retrieve, process, and assess these data. Yet, there is a methodological challenge stemming from the abstract representation of street network data. Since most of the data reflects the topology of transportation-based networks, not every type of analysis can use it directly. Many applications, such as urban morphology (Porta

*martin.fleischmann@natur.cuni.cz

†anvy@itu.dk

‡gaboardijd@ornl.gov

§kryndlea@natur.cuni.cz

¶daniela.dancejova@natur.cuni.cz

et al., 2010), network analysis (Vierø et al., 2024), or drone routing (Morfin Veytia et al., 2023), require a different representation, known as a *morphological* or *centreline representation*, where intersections are represented by single nodes and street segments are represented by single edges. The process of converting a transportation-based network to a morphological network is what we call (street network) simplification. This paper proposes a novel simplification method based on the detection of *face artifacts* (Fleischmann & Vybornova, 2024), i.e., transportation-related artifacts, and continuity properties of the network. The method is released in an open-source Python package: `neatnet`.

Researchers have often resorted to manual simplification, which can be prohibitively time-consuming while being partially irreproducible due to cascading decision biases during the process. Currently, there is a range of tools offering simplification approaches, although often heavily dependent on localised parameters. The most popular is likely the approach in `OSMnx` (Boeing, 2017), which merges all nodes within a certain buffer distance d into one node and recreates edges accordingly. A subsequent step allows the removal of remaining multi-edges by selecting which one to keep. However, the node merging tends to “chain” (in specific configurations) and merge many nodes into a single one resulting in a spider-web-like result. At the same time, the multi-edge simplification does not attempt to create a geometry representing all the edges. Recently, the `cityseer` package (Simons, 2022) introduced another solution that attempts to iteratively collapse both nodes and edges and replace them with new geometries. Similarly to `OSMnx`, there is high dependency either on locally defined parameters or on the availability of OpenStreetMaps tags. The latter issue also affects the applicability of solutions available within the `SNMan` package (Ballo et al., 2024), which further requires manual inputs. Finally, the approach proposed by Lovelace et al. (2024) and released in the `parenx` package (Deakin, 2024) takes the whole network and attempts to recreate it based on either image skeletonization or Voronoi diagram-centreline identification. In both cases, every single geometry is recreated even when no simplification was required. This approach does not preserve edge attributes, while also being highly computationally complex.

2 Continuity-preserving simplification

We propose a novel approach, based on context-aware detection of portions of the network that represent transportation-specific objects, and continuity-aware simplification procedures. As a result, the algorithm can simplify street networks from various geographical contexts using the same set of default parameters, automatically adapting to local peculiarities and scale.

We first ensure the topological correctness of the network, then conservatively consolidate nodes that are very close to each other (approximately 2 meters) to avoid topological issues in subsequent steps. The following procedure forms a loop that we iterate through twice. The loop starts with the detection of face artifacts using the heuristic proposed by Fleischmann and Vybornova (2024). This heuristic polygonizes the network and uses the relationship between the size and shape of the polygons to identify those that are *face artifacts*, i.e., polygons that result from a transportation-oriented mapping and do not represent urban blocks. The face artifacts are then used to identify the portions of the network that require simplification. Other sections of the network remain unaltered by the algorithm. The next step classifies all artifacts into three groups based on artifact

polygon contiguity, and then into several subgroups based on network edge continuity. The first level of classification divides all face artifacts into (1) isolates (polygons with no neighbours), (2) pairs (polygons with a single neighbour), and (3) clusters (polygons with two or more neighbours). Isolates are further classified based on the number of network edges forming the artifact, their continuity properties, and the location(s) of additional vertices. The continuity-based classification is based on the algorithm proposed by Tripathy et al. (2021), implemented in the Python package `momepy` (Fleischmann, 2019). The algorithm identifies continuity strokes as groups of network edges that are *geometrically continuous*, i.e., forming an interior angle above a certain threshold, typically 120 degrees. This approach ensures that continuity is preserved: when a geometry is modified to remove the face artifact, the modification does not significantly alter the continuity of the resulting network. The isolates and pairs are then simplified using continuity-preserving heuristics, while clusters are first merged into a single polygon per cluster and then replaced by a polygon skeleton derived from a Voronoi diagram of their edges. The entire algorithm works purely on top of the geometric representation of the network and does not require any specific attributes linked to the nodes or edges (e.g., hierarchy or road type). Moreover, attributes of the original geometries are not altered in the process.

2.1 Evaluation

Our approach is tested against the procedures available in `OSMnx`, `cityseer` and `parenx`, and additionally compares all of them with manually simplified networks, treated as *ground truth*. To evaluate the performance of our approach, we compare the geometric properties of the simplified networks and the performance of individual implementations on a set of 7 cities sampled from diverse geographical contexts around the globe. Figure 1 compares the outputs of the differing simplification procedures, referenced against the original OSM data, by the example of Place du Congrès in Liège (Belgium).

2.2 Conclusions

The algorithm proposed in this paper provides opportunities for simplification of a large number of networks from various locations in a fully automatised manner, enabling researchers to perform analyses that require morphological street network representation while sourcing globally available transportation-centered data. We believe that our proposed algorithm will be of great use to many network pre-processing pipelines, eliminating data limitations and simplification barriers that are currently present.

2.3 Code and data availability

The final implementation of our adaptive, continuity-preserving simplification algorithm is released in an open-source Python package named `neatnet` with a source code available at <https://github.com/uscuni/neatnet>, alongside fully reproducible code used in the evaluation, available at <https://github.com/uscuni/simplification>.

Figure 1: **Comparing different simplification procedures.** Left panel (black): original OpenStreetMap data of street edges at Place du Congrès in Liège (Belgium). Right multipanel: simplification output of different methods (blue) contrasted with original OSM data (dotted black).

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Biographies

Martin Fleischmann is a Research Associate at the Department of Social Geography and Regional Development at the Charles University in Prague. He leads the Research Team on Urban Structure focusing on cities, from their internal structure or interactions to the evolutionary patterns capturing their past and future.

Anastassia Vybornova is a postdoctoral researcher in Urban Data Science at the Copenhagen Center for Social Data Science (SODAS) at the University of Copenhagen and at the NETwoRks, Data, and Society (NERDS) research group at the IT University of Copenhagen. She has a background in Technical Physics and Environmental Science. Her current work focuses on sustainable mobility and the spatiality of social networks.

James D. Gaboardi is an Associate Research Scientist in the Geospatial Science and Human Security Division at Oak Ridge National Laboratory. He bridges the gap between pure R&D and research software engineering with a background in scientific software development and spatiotemporal modeling, specifically network-based population and facilities.

Anna Brázdová is a Ph.D. student in Social Geography and Regional Development at Charles University, Prague. She is part of the Urban Structure Research Team, with focus on spatial data science.

Daniela Dančejová is currently finishing her Master's degree in Geoinformatics, Cartography, and Remote Sensing at Charles University, Prague. She is part of the Urban Structure Research Team and the Image and Laboratory Spectroscopy Team, with a focus on modeling surface energy fluxes using thermal remote sensing data.

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